

MEDIA ELITE OR POLITICAL ELITE? WHO IS SUPERIOR IN THE WORSENING OF NIGERIA'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL SYSTEM?

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11203738>

Abstract

Democratisation in low-income developing nations is identified to increase corrupt practices among politicians, aided by the media of communication. While threat to life, government interference, injury, intimidations are rife, journalists are the accessories in the pervasive corrupt practices. This study is designed to examine the media elite, political elite, socio-economic and political system with the aim of unravelling the challenges associated with the sectors, and the way out. This paper adopts a qualitative descriptive approach to conduct an in-depth review of available literature to examine the elements involved in media system, political elite, roles of corruption in the socio-political and economic system. The paper conducts empirical studies on political and media elitism based on the findings from the literature review. The paper concludes that it is time Nigerian political elite woke up to their responsibility by providing good governance, which de-emphasizes personal aggrandizement, corruption, ethnocentrism, tribal affiliation, religious sect, to the people.

Keywords: Media Elite, Political Elite, Superiority, Socio-Economic, Political System

INTRODUCTION

Studies are divided about the complicity of both media system and political elitism in the socio-political and economic vulnerabilities of most developing and low-income nations. Nigeria, as an entity, as Jatula (2019) affirms, is defined by media corruption, political corruption, election malfeasance, electioneering hooliganism, ethnic rivalries, and leadership failures. Knowledge and awareness of political events, democratic events and government activities, as Oluwatosin et al., (2020) maintain, increase due to the education and enlightenment functions of the mass media. Mass media have always played the conventional roles of education, entertainment and information in any democratic society. Post-colonial Nigerian nation, as Onyejizu (2021) observes, is ravaged by ethnic rivalries, suspicion and corruption in the wake of independence in 1960. Like politicians and media practitioners, politics and media system, as James and

Abubakri (2017) maintain, are conjoined and inseparable. The vibrancy of the press and popular opposition of the public to certain government activities ensure free democracy (Ogbondah, 1991). Mass media, as Igbino et al., (2020) aver, are crucial in the generation of knowledge, acquisition and dissemination of information designed to meet societal informational needs. Mass media are an indispensable fulcrum on which development of any nation is dependent. In Nigeria, mass media installed democratic process, fought the military to a standstill without the booming of guns. The earliest journalists in Nigeria's democratic experience were thoroughly bred individuals who put patriotism before personal considerations and ethnic or tribal affiliations. The Nigerian first generation of journalists were in the forefront of institutionalization of democracy and civil rule. However, with the passing of time, media active passion and activism in making Nigeria societies better and more competitive in the comity of nations, have given way for corrupt practices, name-calling, propaganda, corrupt editorial practices, imbalanced news coverage among others. Corruption among Nigeria practicing journalist, as Asomah (2023) maintains, has been an impediment to achieving sustainable economic, political and social growth. Media of the global north, as Giglietto et al., (2022) maintain, have ravaged the world with the news delivery system that has created imbalance in the global information platforms, leading to excessive reliance on foreign news and messages that have no bearing on economic, social and cultural development of the people of the developing nations. Democratization in poor and developing nations, unlike in developed and wealthy nations, has been identified to increase corrupt practices among politicians, aided by the media of communication. as Jetter et al., (2015). In most developing nations of the world, many private media organisations are owned and operated by politicians who determine what goes in and comes out as news or information to the public. Most Nigeria politicians, as Oghenekevwe Ifaka et al., (2022) posit, deploy instruments of hunger and poverty to coerce the masses to vote for a political party and its candidates. Widespread greed, self-interest, violence, corruption, intimidation of voters, nepotism and ethnocentrism, as Oyebo (2017) observes, are characteristic of democratic practices in Nigeria. Oyebo (2017) affirms that media are extremely weak in the investigation and coverage of corrupt practices, very lackadaisical in battling the corrupt practices among political class, and are seen to be affected also by the social ills. Mass media have failed to be a unifier of all diverse and pluralistic ethnic nationalities that Nigeria is made up of. Political corruption, as Ordu and Odukwu (2022) aver, represents the use of official positions for personal gains. Corrupt practices, as Onyejizu (2021) maintains, corruption is an impediment to Nigeria's march to sustained development and serves as a root of inter-ethnic conflicts. Media of communication have not been socially responsible to the masses, while the political cycle has been an exclusive preserve of the rich and their offspring. While threat to life, undue interference by government in the management and operations of media organisations, injury lack of laws to protect journalists, enforced disappearance, and intimidation and harassment, Sowunmi et al., (2010), journalists are the accessories in the pervasive corrupt democratic practices in Nigeria. Political leaders, ignoring critical media institutions, according to Badejo et al., (2015), have always been blamed for Nigeria's snail-pace development. While mass media are widely known to mobilise electorate to exercise civic responsibilities, they are also guilty of bias in the coverage and reportage of election-related news (James and Abubakri, 2017). Personnel of Nigerian Police Force have been known to engage in extra-judicial killings, human rights abuses, violations of rights of citizens, torture, and brutality, Akinyetun and Adedini (2022), Nigerian media practitioners have been complicit by the deafening silence of their professional pens. Nigerian successive electoral contests, as Obiam (2021) observes, have always been bedevilled by hate speeches and media-instigated war between and/or political class. While social media, as a medium of mass communication, has provided a platform for citizen-state interactions, Jimada (2019), hate-speeches, cyberbullying, threat and intimidation have been the most discussed and the most shared on the virtual platform. Nigerian media, especially the newspapers have been biased in the coverage and reportage of corruption cases involving individuals as a result of inter-regional factors (Yusha'u, 2010). Like southern newspapers, Northern newspapers, for instance, give more coverage and reportage to a southern politician arrested or alleged to have mismanaged public funds. This study is aimed

at reviewing relevant literature to determine the culpability of either media or political elitism in the socio-economic and political issues that are currently bedeviling Nigeria.

Social Responsibility Theory and Elite Theory

Social responsibility theory was propounded by Siebert Peterson and Wilbur Schramm in 1963. The major premise of the theory is that media, as an institution, should accept and fulfil certain obligations to society (Anaeto, Onabajo and Osifeso, 2008). The study is anchored on the social responsibility theory because media, by rule, have to be socially responsible to the people in the existence and operations. Media have obligations not to only hold those at the helms of affairs of Nigeria accountable to the governed, but also must give a voice to the voiceless. The re-evaluation of social responsibility media system came into being, as Aina (2003) posits, due to the commercial development of the press had curtailed some people's access to information and only a single class freely used the media to consolidate power. The media, as Aina (2003) avers, should accept and fulfil certain obligations to the society, and these obligations are to be met by setting high professional standards of informativeness, truth, accuracy, objectivity and balance and in accepting and applying these obligations, the media should be self-regulating within the framework of the law and established institutions. The media, as Aina (2003) maintains, should avoid what might lead to crime, violence or civil disorder or give offence to minority groups. This development tasked the social responsibility principles to reconcile individual freedom and media choice with media obligation to the society. The media, as the social responsibility system posit, have the responsibility to serve the political system by making information, discussion and consideration of public affairs generally accessible and to inform the public to enable it take informed and self-determined actions (Anaeto et al., 2008). The social responsibility media system, as Folarin (1998) opines, an inordinate concern for professionalism tends to make the media slavish to technology at the expense of pressing social norms, such as the rights of women, children and minorities.

This study is, in addition to social responsibility theory, anchored on elite theory. The basic assumption of elite theory is that elite in any society use political power and media of communication to consolidate their hold on power. Elite theory, as Arslan (2005) notes, aims to explain power structure and relations in a state. While it is common knowledge that elite in African continent are important political actors, Osei (2008), their actual roles have been under-theorized and ignored in empirical research. The elite, according to Yapa (2014), play a dominant role by in legitimizing their absolute power using media of communication to influence attitudes, behaviour and thoughts of the poor masses. Elite theory, according Campati (2022), postulates that in any human society, age and history a fragment of the population tends to concentrate in their own hands commonwealth and resources meant for all and continually impose itself on all others who lack the resources or power. One of the means by which elite initiate and maintain their political stronghold is by way of politics and media. Evidently, an unfair and imbalanced distribution and control of resources in a society result in an unequal distribution of power (Campati, 2022). There are two class of citizens, as Campati, (2022) notes: the government or rulers and the governed. The former are a handful of individuals, who are capable, due resources within their reach, of grabbing and monopolizing power, while the later are of greater population, but are controlled and directed by the former in an arbitrary and violent manner (Campati, 2022).

Media Elite Versus Political Elite

The quest for sound leadership and good governance have always been a staple for public discussion, Aluko (2021), and media roles and influences cannot be dwarfed in this democratic process. As Omitola (2021) opines, most investigative reports are about embezzlement of public funds and emanate from the government whose main responsibilities are to protect the lives, property of the citizenry, and prevent

corrupt practices in high and low paces in the society. Media, as Jatula (2020) opines, have placed tangible and intangible financial interests over public interests in Nigeria. Free press and functioning democracy, as Okafor (2022) posits, are the two fundamentals for sustainable societal development. The media, regarded as powerful shaper of public opinions, as Jatula (2020) opines, are recruited by politicians and political parties to influence public perception to have favourable election outcomes. Political elite maintain antagonistic stance against the press. Although, free press has been very fundamental in a function democracy. Invasion of privacy, unfair coverage and reportage of information, one-sided news analysis, as Jatula (2019) avers, have been the hallmarks of media practice in Nigerian democratic experience. As Mustapha et al., (2022) observe, most people in West African Sub-region face challenges of trust in news media for sources of information, education and other enlightenment messages. State-owned and private-owned media are biased organs and megaphones of government in power (Jatula, 2019). Some private-owned media bent on ethical practices are cut off from lucrative state-run political campaigns and other government messages (Jatula, 2019). Political corruption is an impediment on the march of Nigeria to sustainable development. While political elite are the drivers of government and economy, Media elite represent suppliers of information and providers of education, owners and its operators. Political elite have an unhindered access to state resources with which they prosecute elections and keep themselves perpetually in power. Media of communication have been identified to have power of to educate, mobilize, inform and rescue the people from political apathy, Chukwuma (2022), media responsibilities have always been one-sided. Media could either be owned by government or private individuals. Government interference in media operations, either owned by government or private individual, is not far to seek. Therefore, media elite and political elite are the conjoined and inseparable entities, working together to build or to destroy the very fabric of a society. Intra- and inter-regional factors, as Yusha'u (2010) maintains, play a crucial role in the coverage and reportage of corruption cases in Nigeria. Corruption, as Di and Shem (2018) posit, has permeated all spheres of Nigerian national life, and other sectors including the media institutions are not exempted from the social ill. The watchdog roles of Nigerian media practice, as James and Olusola (2015) have maintained, have given way to lapdog roles, and the media in Nigeria have transitioned from the vociferous to the quiet, active to passive, and corruption-free to corruption-infested. Political interference and ownership factors, as C (2018) maintains, are the impediments to a fair journalistic practice and true media practice in Nigeria. Influences of advertisers and big sponsors of the media, as C (2018) observes, have robbed the masses of rights to undiluted news, education and entertainment. Like Politicians, Nigerian media practitioners perpetrate economic and financial crimes through money-laundering, fraud, economic sabotage undue influence-seeking, and impersonations (Oluwadamilare and Ekwueme, 2020). Economic and financial crimes, as Oluwadamilare and Ekwueme (2020) observe, by political elite and criminal silence by the media elite have constrained Nigeria's march towards sustainable development. Public-interest journalism, as Okafor (2022) maintains, has given way for money-and politics-interest journalism in Nigeria. money, media and politics are the inseparable musketeers. However, money and media system, as Ologbenla and Adisa (2012) posit, have always been fraudulently deployed by Nigerian politicians to influence election outcomes. Media influence in democratic process, according to Jatula (2020), is being questioned going by the prevalence of political corruption and social injustice. Media distrust and eroding confidence members of the public have about the press, strengthened by lopsidedness in the coverage and reportage of news, excessive financial interest of the media and corrupt practices have all worked together to erode the trust in Nigerian media system. While coverage and reportage of corruption related-issues could put the corrupter and corrupt practices under check, Nzeaka et al., (2022), media men and women, either by blood, through education, or tribe, are the associates of the corrupt political office holders. And by this, press or media men and women have worsened the political, and socio-economic system in excess of the political elite, who are the drivers of the economy, political power, and the custodians or few beneficiaries of the common wealth and resources meant for the poor masses.

Media and Nigeria's Socio-Economic and Political System

There have been scholarly debates about relationship between media, corruption and political system. As Duhu (2019) posits, corruption can affect the economic growth of a nation negatively. Nigerian media, as Enobi and Oyedokun (2014) assert, play a significant role in raising awareness about the issue of corrupt practices, especially in the public sector of the economy. Nigerian media system has always been accused of placing a premium on lucrative advertisements, political parties and politicians rather than editorial responsibilities (Jatula, 2020). Nigerian political system, as Ologbenla and Adisa (2012) maintain, is dominated by corruption and money and media have also been deployed by politicians to grab power and to perpetuate themselves in office. Political elite, in conjunction with the media system owned and managed, and even regulated by the political elite, are responsible for the nation's underdevelopment. Although, political competition reduces the risk of corruption among political office seekers, Brueckner (2022), political money-bags have the resources to grab power against the will of the populace. However, the media, established to keep the government responsible to the governed should carry more blame in the process of underdevelopment of Nigeria. Political elite, as Onah et al., (2022) aver, engage in anti-people policies such as nepotism in the appointment and recruitment process, looting of common wealth, electoral fraud and violence, among others. Nigeria, as Ahmad et al., (2023) aver, is faced with issues of regionalism, inter-ethnic and inter-tribal violence, corruption, unemployment, low economic growth, electoral violence, kidnapping and inter-political party crisis. Nigeria earns millions of dollars from the crude oil sales, Onah et al., (2022), and she has the opportunities to be among the rich nations of the world, with economic development and equitable political process and the well-being of her citizens. As Onah et al., (2022) assert, Nigeria ranks abysmally low in all yardsticks for measuring development and economic growth, cum good life among the countries of the world, due to political corruption and inefficient justice system. In the international system, Nigeria has always been described as a nation in crises. Crises of Boko Haram, ethnic militias, corruption, electoral violence dot the airwaves and pages of international media (Pierce, 2006). Good governance in the areas of economic, socio and political advancements, as Gyong (2022) posits, are the fundamentals for attainment of full potentials in Nigeria's democratic experiments. Corruption in Nigeria has grown to become a cankerworm, and the effectiveness of the anti-graft agencies to defeat corruption and corrupt practices have always been questioned (Ewa et al., 2019).

Media and Nigerian Security System

While people are more interested in security issues, Olise (2020), Nigerian media are more interested in the coverage and reportage of political issues, politicians, and activities of political parties. Studies have long established that media in Nigeria give more prominence of terrorist attacks than the successes of the military or the Police in the fight against Boko Haram and other security challenges witnessed in Nigeria. Nigerian media have been alleged of bias against the Police and Military men, Ndinojuo et al., (2020) and other security outfits priming and framing Boko Haram, Eastern Security Network, Odua Peoples' Congress, and other ethnic militias as being superior in the use of firearms, making better armed security officers afraid of confronting the terrorists. The number of soldiers Boko Haram killed, kidnapped or wounded usually adorned the pages of the Nigerian newspapers or grabbed the news headlines of most radio and television stations. Having a balanced news coverage and reportage is a generally accepted norm, but media bias is very conspicuous in the coverage and reportage of security-related matters in Nigeria. Although, Nigerian security sectors are embroiled so deep in corruption and corrupt practices, the Nigerian media sectors are not any better (James and Olusola, 2015). Security personnel and political hooligans, as Ujene and

Ojedokun (2021) have been identified as the main perpetrators of violence against media men and women. Due to their mode of operations, security operatives always detest the presence of the media men (Ujene and Ojedokun, 2021). As a result of government influences, Obiam (2021), various shades of under-reported electoral violence have characterized the conduct of national election since the beginning of fourth republic in 1999.

Media social Responsibilities and Political Influences

There have been controversies on the relationship between media responsibilities and political. All humans are political animals. The gate-keepers in media houses are sympathetic to the course of one political party or the other. However, no media in Nigeria is totally objective in its news coverage and reportage due to some certain constraints that media operators face in their daily routine. According to James and Abubakri (2017) ownership factors determine the nature of media practice and the kind of information to be expected from the such media. Like judicial system in Nigeria, which is subjected to the interference of the executive arm of the government, no media organization is totally independent of government interference and rich advertisers. As James (2019) opines, media should be socially responsible to the governed and give prominence to issues that border on the lives of ordinary citizens. However, events have shown that media are totally independent of political interference due to certain unavoidable factors among which are the ownership style and legal considerations (James and Olusola, 2015). Governments, in young and old democracies, have the social responsibilities of keeping the government on its toes and keep the government responsible to the governed (Omitola, 2021). Media practice in sub-Sahara Africa, as Schiffrin (2010) notes, is limited by issues of government pressure and interference, poor resources, ownership factor and declining sound professional training. Radio, television and newspaper, as Schiffrin (2010) avers, are not effective in the performances of their social responsibilities due to constraints encountered by journalists. Reports of violence and hooganism that characterized the conduct of electoral process in Nigeria are not available in the public space by the media (Genyi, 2015). The democratization of politics in Nigeria, as Nwagwu et al., (2018) observe, has not reduced the issues of corruption, ballot box snatching. Political hooliganism, vote-buying and vote-selling in Nigeria's democratic experiments.

Methodology

This study adopts qualitative method to address socio-political and economic issues with regard to media system and political elitism. The issues of political elite and media elite never received the research attention of scholars and researchers in social sciences, journalism and mass communication studies. Media sectors are important institutions of any nation, which have the leverage to make or mar the development of such nation, and are also crucial in the rebirth and regeneration of a nation. However, studies have long established than media sectors are accessories in the institutionalization of corruption in Nigeria, rather than its fighter. This paper therefore adopts a qualitative method to conduct an in-depth review of available literature to examine the elements involved in media and political elite and roles of corruption in the socio-political and economic system of Nigeria. The paper conducts empirical studies on political and media elitism based on the findings from the literature review, while also suggesting theories to guide the study. The reviewed sources include reference books, journals, and other written materials linked to the issues.

Recommendations

Strong and committed journalist unions, unbiased investigative journalism, Free press, independence of judiciary, vibrant civil society organisations, and strong anti-corruption institutions are extremely crucial

to attain socio-economic and political development in Nigeria. strong institutions give birth to a strong society, devoid of nepotism, ethnic rivalry, corruption and social injustice. Absolute power inherent in Nigerian leadership should be questioned by relevant organs such as media, judiciary and the legislature. Civil society organisations should be strengthened to provide voice to those deemed to be voiceless in Nigeria.

Low adherence to social responsibility dictates of the media and the developmental principles by media practitioners, as Kolawole and Ojebuyi (2019) maintain, have untold consequences on democratic practice and societal development. Media organisation have to be trained and re-trained to understand the basic media social responsibility and developmental principles aimed at exposing them to basic requirements of functional democracy.

It is time Nigerian political elite woke up to their responsibility by providing good governance, which de-emphasizes personal aggrandizement, corruption, ethnocentrism, tribal affiliation, religious sect, to the people. Competent, incorruptible and people of integrity should be encouraged to seek for political offices (Nwanne, 2017).

Although, some private media organisations are interested in investigative journalism, government rules and regulations have clipped their wings with regard to invasion of privacy, confidentiality, free speech, hate speech, and threat, intimidation, kidnapping, enforced disappearances and assassination attempts from non-state actors have worked together to silence the media. However, civil society organisations and government have a role to play, like judiciary, members of the press should be protected by armed security operatives provided by the government.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Introduction and Literature Review, J. A., Methodology and Abstract, F. F. and Referencing and Recommendations, O. M. R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

No funding was received

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not Applicable

Informed Consent Statement: Not Applicable

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: No conflict of interest

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